

Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability - IG

RDA Plenary 16

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Kheeran Dharmawardena

Cytrax Consulting

Agenda

- **Introduction to Social Dynamics group - Kheeran (15 min)**
- **Presentation - Social architecture - Ashlin Lee (15 min)**
- **Introduction to MIRO (5 min)**
- **Discussion - What constitutes organisational interoperability? (50 min)**
 - **Discussion on what does it mean to have organisational interoperability?**
 - **What does it look like? Are there good examples?**
 - **What are the observable elements that exist to understand the level of interoperability that can be achieved by organisations?**
- **(5 min) Wrap up**

Housekeeping

- Please be aware that this session is being recorded.
- Interactive session, so speak up and participate.
- We will be using Miro as a tool for collaboration today
 - <https://bit.ly/2It7dZk>

Why do we need a focus on Social dynamics?

Data lives in business units and projects

Data is still hard to discover, access and use

Data lives in complex ecosystem – systems, institutions, people

Data supply chains have a mix of formal and informal arrangements

Complex ecosystems

Complex ecosystems

Complex ecosystems

Complex ecosystems

Why do we need a focus on Social dynamics?

The Australian Research Data Cloud should broadly align with the European Open Science Cloud and other global initiatives. It should support research data management from creation and discovery, through description and provenance, integration and storage, manipulation and analysis, and preservation.

2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap
<https://www.education.gov.au/2016-national-research-infrastructure-roadmap>

CHALLENGES AND GENERAL OBSERVATIONS

- The majority of the challenges to reach a functional EOSC are social rather than technical.
- The major technical challenge is the complexity of the data and analytics procedures across disciplines rather than the size of the data per se.

A clash of cultures?

A 'clash of cultures' emerged as a key challenge⁶ from the stakeholder consultation, as historical developments may have led to a chasm between domain specialists and e-infrastructure specialists. Open Science drives two very different communities and cultures together and we lack connective tissue. In the earlier transition of scientific research from a loosely individual elite and intellectual activity to a mainstream, institute-based activity,

Realising the European Open Science Cloud report
http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf?view=fit&pagemode=none

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) builds the social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of data.

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation and National Institute of Standards and Technology, and the Australian Government's Department of Innovation with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data.

Sandpits & Engine rooms, Pioneers & Town Planners

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Multidisciplinary Approach

Patterns

(32) Large platforms lead to interoperable/standard data

Data standards and interoperability is increased when the data is held by, aggregated through or managed by large platforms. The size enables scale, which leads to others adopting same standards as used by the platform or developing things that interoperate with the large platform.

Solutions:

(35) Getting data to the facility (anti-pattern)

Context
Potential data providers are currently not contributing data to the facility.

Problem
We have invested in a data facility to enable our researchers in the related research domain to deposit and share research data. However we know that researchers are still keeping their data to themselves and not shar

Solutions

- Lowering the barriers to ingesting data;
- Grants require or encourage the data generated through grant funded activities
- Incorporate facility as part of the workflow of creating & analysing the data;
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Exam

(02) In the Limelight

Context
In a group (eg: CRC), the publicity around activities is necessary for the growth and sustainability of the group.

Problem
The publicity is necessary for the group, however, if it is not shared amongst the participants in an equitable way, it can leave individuals feeling like they've lost the limelight and lead to dissent amongst the group members.

Solutions
Find ways of sharing the limelight amongst the group members in equitable ways.

Consequences

Related patterns

(34) Attracting (the right) users

Context
The VL that aims to bring together several distinct disciplines but we see that one of the key challenges is in getting the two groups to work together.

Problem

(31) Maturing of the Startup

uccessful grow and hit a tipping point in their existence. This occurs when they no ct provides, and instead people come seeking to make use of what they provide. jceed till now fail to provide the same level of value and often impede it. At this s to continue to survive and grow.

Objective of this Interest Group

From the (proposed) Charter:

1. Identify organisational, institutional, economic, and individual aspects that increase the friction to achieving information interoperability.
2. Develop a corpus of knowledge, including models, frameworks and patterns that can be applied by practitioners to develop the desired social dynamics that reduce friction and foster information interoperability.
3. Identify and develop case studies of solutions that demonstrate the application of the corpus of knowledge on this topic. It is acknowledged that often the details of specific case studies could be sensitive and documented case studies may need to be synthesised drawing upon actual cases.

Thank you